

LE-PAROLE

WP2.11

Italian Corpus Documentation

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<i>To</i>	PTC		Validation

1. Structure of the corpus

Medium	Planned number of words (T24)	Percentage of total corpus (T24)
BOOKS	3,600,000	18%
NEWSPAPERS	13,900,000	69.5%
PERIODICALS	900,00	4.5%
MISCELLANEOUS	1,600,000	8%
TOTAL	20,000,000	100%

2. Selection and Collection of the texts

Books:

Source	Timespan/Date	State of agreement	Total (T24) estimated no. of words	T18 (Current) no. of words converted or convertible
Elemond	1970-1995	agreement in principle	1,400,000	1,400,000
Einaudi	1970-1995	agreement in principle	2,200,000	2,200,000
Sub-total for Books			3,600,000	3,600,000

Newspapers:

Source	Time span/Date	State of agreement	Total (T24) estimated no. of words	T18 (Current) no. of words converted or convertible
"La Repubblica"	1992-1996	signed, with restrictions (for research purposes only)	3,090,000	3,569,000
"Il Corriere della Sera"	1992-1996	signed, with restrictions	3,090,000	3,231,000
"La Stampa"	1992-1996	signed, with restrictions	3,090,000	3,293,000
"Il Sole-24 Ore"	1992-1996	signed with restrictions	4,100,000	4,152,000

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"L'Unione Sarda"	March 1996	signed, with restrictions	530,000	530,000
Sub-total for Newspapers			13,900,000	14,775,000

Periodicals:

Source	Time span/Date	State of agreement	Total (T24) estimated no. of words	T18 (Current) no. of words converted or convertible
Mondadori Editore Milano	1985-1988	signed, with restrictions (for research purposes only)	900,000	900,000
Sub-total for Periodicals			900,000	900,000

Miscellaneous:

Source	Time span/Date	State of agreement	Total (T24) estimated no. of words (in million)	T18 (Current) no. of words converted or convertible
CNR: -rules and decrees;	1992/1993	full	453,000	453,000
- description of research projects;	1992		886,000	886,000
-description of patents;	1987/1991		60,000	60,000
-description of research activity	1995		89,000	89,000
Various	-	-	112,000	-
Sub-total for Misc.			1,600,000	1,488,000

TOTAL (Books, Newspapers, Periodicals, Misc.)			20,000,000	17,500,000
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Selection criteria by Medium:

Newspapers:

Our selection criteria for newspapers are based on the following assumptions:

- we include entire newspaper issues;
- the choice of the issues aims to ensure a regular distribution of the material over a year and also over the 5 year period.
- for each newspaper, the number of words per year is equally distributed over a 12 month range;
- the selection of issues aims to cover all the days of the week and to prevent issues from different newspapers being chosen from the same day during the 5 year period.

Application of selection criteria:

- Total amount of words: 13,9 million.
- We have decided to divide this amount in the following ways: 66.6% for national press (3 newspapers: “La Repubblica”, “Il Corriere della Sera”, “La Stampa”), 29.8% for specialised press (“Il Sole-24 Ore”, a financial newspaper) and 3.6% for regional press (“L’Unione Sarda”).

Periodicals:

The periodicals concern various topics: “Casaviva” (monthly home magazine), “Centocose” (monthly magazine for teenagers), “Epoca” (weekly general magazine), “Espansione” (computational economics monthly magazine), “Grazia” (women’s weekly magazine), “Panorama” (weekly general magazine), “Starbene” (monthly health magazine), “Storia Illustrata” (monthly history magazine), “Zerouno” (computer science monthly magazine).

They cover a 4 year time period (1985-1988). These texts have all been extracted from the ILC Italian Reference Corpus, thereby reusing available data for this medium.

The total amount of words is distributed over the nine periodicals (approx. 100,000 words each).

We have selected an average number of 2 issues per year for each periodical.

Books:

Currently, we are working on entire books.

At the end of the project we will have a set of about 60 books providing us with the chosen amount of material for this medium.

Miscellaneous:

For the moment we have processed bureaucratic (rules and decrees) and technical (descriptions of CNR patents and research projects) documents from the central CNR offices.

At the same time, we are also working to collect material from other sources (i.e., official material from Livorno Town Council) to reach the required amount of words for this medium.

Our aim is to collect material from various sources in order to be able to differentiate this medium as much as possible: in case we would have at disposal a good amount of texts, we will proceed to eliminate some CNR documents (i.e., rules and decrees) so as to insert more varied kind of material (commercial letters, issues from a parish magazine, etc.).

3. Use of the Corpus DTD

During the phase of preparation of texts for the SGML conversion we decided to encode the following non-obligatory elements:

Header

In the SGML text header we maintain all descriptive information present in newspapers and periodicals sources.

They usually concern:

- “themes” and nouns of places, persons, organisations, events;
- sections and columns where the article can be found.

All of this information is put in the header, in the <KEYWORDS> section using the SGML tag <TERM TYPE=*‘according to the type of information’*>.

The following table lists all the type of keywords encoded:

Evento (<i>Event</i>)	<TERM TYPE=“E”>
Società (<i>Organisation</i>)	<TERM TYPE=“S”>
Persone (<i>People</i>)	<TERM TYPE=“P”>
Argomenti (<i>Themes</i>)	<TERM TYPE=“T”>
Luoghi Geografici (<i>Places</i>)	<TERM TYPE=“L”>
Nomi (<i>Proper Nouns</i>)	<TERM TYPE=“N”>
Genere-“Kind” (occurring <i>only in one newspaper, “La Stampa”</i> ; the same information is given both in Italian (<i>Genere</i>) and in	<TERM TYPE=“K”>

<i>English(Kind)</i>	
Testo Citato (<i>Reference made to any work - play, TV programme book, picture and so on - cited in the text</i>)	<TERM TYPE="Y">
Inserto (<i>Supplement</i>)	<TERM TYPE="I">
Sezione (<i>Section</i>)	<TERM TYPE="Z">
Rubrica (<i>Column</i>)	<TERM TYPE="R">

Later on we will insert the GENRE and TOPIC categories in the <CATREF> section.

The Name of the Author of the text is also encoded in the header and in particular it is found in the <TITLESTMT><AUTHOR> and in the <BIBLSTRUCT><MONOGR><AUTHOR>

Body

	Corresponding SGML Tag
signature of an article	<NAME TYPE='author'>
signature of a newspaper/periodical letter	<NAME TYPE='signatory'>
date of the text at the beginning of newspaper and periodical articles	<DATE> in the <OPENER> tag
titles: main title half-title summary sub-title	<HEAD TYPE='title'> <HEAD TYPE='half-title'> <HEAD TYPE='summary'> <HEAD TYPE='sub'>
caption	<CAPTION N='unspec'>
table: caption of the table table	<CAPTION N='attached'> Articles made up only by a table are deleted. Other tables are, for the moment, marked with the tag <-- --> but not converted.
correction of misspelt word	<CORR SIC='error'>correct word</CORR>
abbreviation abbreviation dot	<ABBR> &p2; (<i>the entity reference is used to distinguish this abbreviation dot from the full stop</i>)
dots	… (<i>the entity reference is used to distinguish this character from the full stop</i>)
hyphen	‐ (<i>the entity reference is used to distinguish the hyphen from the dash</i>)
omission of parts of text: piece of text lacking in the source piece of text removed by us for	<GAP REASON='Piece of text lacking in the source'>

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a different reason	<GAP REASON='Unrelevant piece of text'>
page number	<(pa)PAGE N='number of the page'> in the <OPENER> tag
see (e.g., see page 25) at the end of a newspaper article	<CLOSER>
highlighted	<HI TYPE="bold">; <HI TYPE="italics">
note	<NOTE PLACE='END'>
punctuation within numbers: dot comma dash slash	&p1; &va; &to; &ba; <i>(these entity references are used to distinguish the special use of punctuation marks within numbers)</i>

3.1 Strategy of work

Our work from the sources to the final SGML format is structured in the following way:

- automatic conversion of the source to our internal DBT format (DBT = textual data base allowing linguistic text queries);
- manual checking of the texts to encode all elements at and below the paragraph level described in the table above;
- use of a spelling checker: manual mark-up of errors and, in addition, insertion of the word considered to be the correct one ;
- automatic conversion of the DBT archives to the SGML format.

The necessary conversion programs have been tested and t12 newspaper material (see table in section 2) is available in SGML format.

4. Linguistic Annotation

Text or medium	number of words POS tagged and checked (in thousands) *	number of words tagged and checked for maximum granularity
Newspapers ("Il Sole-24	130,000	100,000

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Ore”, “La Repubblica”, “Il Corriere della Sera”) Periodicals (a sub-set of articles from all of them)		
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- *This table refers to t18. [It should be noted that the words POS tagged are less than the required quantity at t18 because we decided to tag all the words with the maximum granularity. This choice involves a slower pace of work in the tagging phase.]

Note that we also add the lemma to tagged words.

The ILC linguistic annotation phase is composed of three steps:

- the automatic tagging of our texts with the PiTagger procedure (part of the PiSystem whose engine is the DBT query system, developed by E. Picchi, ILC). It is based on the DMI (Dizionario Macchina dell’Italiano - Italian Machine-Readable Dictionary) and on the Italian Morphology (PiMorpho);
- the post-editor step of the tagging procedure. Using an appropriate interactive program of the procedure itself, the tags automatically proposed by the PiTagger are cross-checked by two linguists;
- automatic conversion of the tags proposed by the PiTagger to the PAROLE tagset.

5. Remaining work

Genre and Topic

Classification by GENRE and TOPIC is optional according to the PAROLE Technical Annex. At the moment, we are designing a procedure to automatically convert existing keywords of newspapers and periodicals into the GENRE and TOPIC categories.

GENRE and TOPIC will be manually assigned to books and to miscellaneous material.

SGML conversion

SGML conversion programs are ready for newspapers texts only.

As concerns the remaining material processed till now, programs for conversion should have not been prepared yet.

This phase of programming will require a certain amount of work since the material is varied and needs attention to the peculiarities proper to each text.

Newspapers

We still have to process 5-6 issues from "Il Corriere della Sera" (that means to convert them in DBT format) and then to prepare them for the SGML conversion. This work should not present any kind of problem, considering that we have worked on this type of material before and that the conversion has been successfully executed.

Periodicals

All the material is available for the SGML conversion. No problems are foreseen.

Books

We have concluded the phase of conversion from the sources (ILC Reference Corpus) to the DBT format.

The material is then available for the final SGML conversion.

Miscellaneous

We are successfully carrying on the collection process for this medium.

Till now we have about 1,4 million words ready to be converted in DBT format.

As already mentioned in the above tables, it should be kept in mind that data concerning the miscellaneous material (both information on figures and kind of sources) are liable to be altered during the phase of collection.

This is due to the desire to differentiate as much as possible the material of this medium.

Tagging

We do not expect any problems, given the past experience in tagging work.